

Biomarkers for Cardiotoxicity-Relevant Key Events in Human Cardiac *In Vitro* Models

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Project summary:

The **S2TOX** - “*Mechanistic Assessment of Cardiotoxicity using Integrated In Silico and In Vitro Modeling*” project is an interdisciplinary initiative designed to replace traditional animal testing with a human-relevant, *in vitro-in silico* platform for evaluating drug-induced cardiotoxicity (DICT). Using anthracyclines as a primary case study, the project aims to mechanistically explain and predict how cardiac damage varies according to a patient’s sex and age.

S2TOX is structured into four Work Packages (WP):

- WP1 (*in silico* modeling): Optimizing an Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) network and building a probabilistic Boolean model parameterized with human transcriptomics data.
- WP2 (*in vitro* testing): Establishing a human iPSC-derived cardiac organoid platform to generate functional and omics data for model calibration.
- WP3 (validation & trials): Validating the model against the organoid data and conducting virtual clinical trials to profile toxicity mechanisms across different patient profiles.
- WP4 (management & training): Open science dissemination, data management, and professional development.

Background:

This dataset serves as a critical preliminary catalogue for the **S2TOX** project, addressing the significant challenge of DICT, which is a leading cause of drug failure. It lists mechanism-specific Key Events (KEs) alongside corresponding biomarkers and assay methods using human-relevant models, particularly human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMs). These physiologically relevant *in vitro* models allow for the assessment of various cardiotoxic hazards, including electrophysiology, contractility, structural toxicity, and metabolic function.

These defined biomarkers and corresponding high-throughput screening (HTS) methods are extremely useful for S2TOX by enabling the rapid, human-relevant, and mechanistically informative assessment of chemical hazards. Ultimately, leveraging these biomarkers allows S2TOX to achieve a complete view of molecular responses and potentially rank the cardiotoxicity risk of novel drug candidates based on cellular mechanisms observed in human cell models.

Table 1 lists the heart-related key events from the cardiotoxicity adverse outcome pathway (AOP) network with their biomarkers and relevant references

Table 1. Key Event Biomarkers

Key Event (KE)	Biomarkers	Relevant References
ACh Synaptic Accumulation (KE10) – Excess acetylcholine in synapses leading to cholinergic overstimulation.	<p>Acetylcholine level (metabolomic): measure ACh in culture medium by ELISA or colorimetric assay.</p> <p>Beat rate (electrophysiology): increased ACh causes slowed beating (bradycardia). In MEA assays, acetylcholine/carbachol or organophosphate AChE inhibitors cause an ~10% drop in beat frequency.</p> <p>FPD prolongation (electrophysiology): excess AChE inhibition prolongs field potential duration in hiPSC-CMs.</p>	(Amend et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Honda et al., 2021)
AChE Inhibition (KE12) – Inhibition of acetylcholinesterase (leading to KE10).	<p>AChE enzymatic activity (biochemical): measure AChE activity in cell lysate (Ellman colorimetric assay). A significant drop from baseline indicates inhibition (biomarker of KE12).</p> <p>ACh accumulation (metabolomic): following AChE inhibition, measure ACh build-up in medium (ELISA).</p> <p>Cholinergic functional effects: slowed beat rate or arrhythmias on MEA (see KE10). Cyclosarin (AChE inhibitor) induced FPD prolongation (~9–10%) in hiPSC-CMs.</p>	(Amend et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Krishna et al., 2021)
Altered Action Potential (KE698) – Any change in cardiomyocyte action potential morphology.	<p>AP duration & shape (electrophysiology): Patch-clamp or voltage-sensitive dyes to record AP in iPSC-CMs. Biomarkers include a shortened or prolonged AP plateau phase and decreased AP amplitude or upstroke velocity.</p> <p>Field potential metrics (electrophysiology): MEA-derived FPD changes (e.g. prolonged FPD as surrogate for APD prolongation).</p> <p>EADs (arrhythmia marker): secondary depolarisations during AP in patch recordings.</p>	(Amend et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Li et al., 2016; Sager et al., 2014; Sharma et al., 2018; Wells et al., 2019)
Altered Cardiovascular Development/Function (KE317) – Disruption of developmental or functional programmes.	<p>Gene expression (transcript): e.g., downregulation of cardiac developmental genes (e.g., NKX2-5, SOX9) by qPCR/RNA-seq.</p> <p>Structural markers (imaging): abnormal sarcomere architecture (α-actinin staining) or myocyte alignment.</p> <p>Functional readouts: in developing tissue constructs, reduced contractile function (twitch force) and altered calcium transients indicate developmental defects.</p>	(Burnett et al., 2021; Gawdzik et al., 2018; Lyon et al., 2022; Shankar & Villeneuve, 2023; Westerhoff et al., 2025)
Cardiac Hypertrophy (KE2001) – Enlargement of cardiomyocytes.	<p>Cell size (imaging): increased cardiomyocyte area (immunofluorescence for α-actinin); detected by high-content microscopy.</p> <p>Foetal gene expression (transcript/protein): upregulation of NPPA/ANP and NPPB/BNP mRNA and protein (qPCR/ELISA). Johansson et al. 2020 found an ~13% larger cell size and an ~5–10\times rise in ANP/BNP in hiPSC-CMs with ET-1 hypertrophic stimulus.</p> <p>Protein synthesis (metabolic): increased total protein per cell (indicative of hypertrophic growth).</p>	(Bhutani et al., 2025; Burnett et al., 2021; Georgiadis et al., 2022; Johansson et al., 2020; Moazeni et al., 2017)

<p>Cell Injury/Death (KE55) – Cardiomyocyte damage or death.</p>	<p>Cardiac troponins (proteomic): release of troponin I or T into medium (ELISA); established marker of cardiomyocyte injury. Anthracycline studies show troponin release precedes functional decline.</p> <p>LDH leakage (enzymatic): elevated lactate dehydrogenase in culture supernatant indicates membrane damage.</p> <p>Apoptosis markers (biochemical/imaging): caspase-3/7 activation (luminescent assay) or Annexin V binding/TUNEL staining (imaging flow cytometry).</p>	<p>(Adamcova et al., 2019; Afrin et al., 2022; Bhutani et al., 2025; Moazeni et al., 2017; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Decrease, Calcium Binding to Troponin C (KE1531) – Reduced Ca²⁺ affinity of troponin.</p>	<p>Calcium sensitivity (functional): measure shift in tension-calcium curve in engineered heart tissues or single cells (e.g., using skinned fibres or engineered tissue strips). Decreased Ca-binding lowers force at a given [Ca²⁺].</p> <p>Contraction amplitude (electrophysiology): reduced fractional shortening or twitch force (motion imaging or force transducers) despite normal Ca transient amplitude.</p> <p>Troponin isoforms (proteomic/transcript): changes in troponin subunit expression by Western blot or qPCR.</p>	<p>(Adamcova et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Mamoshina et al., 2021; Salhi et al., 2014; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Decrease, Calcium Currents (KE1530) – Reduced L-type or other Ca²⁺ currents.</p>	<p>ICa,L (electrophysiology): whole-cell patch clamp of iPSC-CMs to measure L-type Ca²⁺ current amplitude. A significant reduction indicates this KE.</p> <p>Calcium transient amplitude (imaging): Fluo-4 or FLIPR Ca²⁺ imaging; smaller peak Ca transient suggests reduced Ca influx.</p> <p>AP plateau (electrophysiology): shortened AP plateau in patch or optical recordings due to reduced ICa,L.</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Miyoshi et al., 2025; Sharma et al., 2018; Shen et al., 2000)</p>
<p>Decrease, Cardiac Contractility (KE1532) – Reduced force generation.</p>	<p>Contractile force (functional): measurement of twitch force in engineered heart tissue or muscle strips (force transducers).</p> <p>Fractional shortening (imaging): % cell-length shortening or pixel displacement of monolayers under video microscopy or impedance assays.</p> <p>Peak Ca transient or beat amplitude (imaging): lower amplitude Ca transients or contraction velocity in iPSC-CM syncytia (optical mapping/MEA).</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Honda et al., 2021; Li et al., 2016; Miyoshi et al., 2025; Sharma et al., 2018; Sirenko et al., 2017; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Decrease, SOX9 Expression (KE2020) – Downregulation of SOX9.</p>	<p>SOX9 mRNA/protein (transcript/protein): decreased SOX9 levels by qPCR or Western blot.</p>	<p>(Gawdzik et al., 2018; Shankar & Villeneuve, 2023; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Decreased, Sodium Conductance 1 (KE585) – Reduced Nav1.5 current.</p>	<p>INa (electrophysiology): whole-cell patch clamp of iPSC-CMs; decreased peak inward Na⁺ current amplitude.</p> <p>dV/dt max (electrophysiology): slowed AP upstroke velocity in patch or optical AP recordings.</p> <p>SCN5A expression (transcript): lowered Nav1.5 mRNA by qPCR.</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Li et al., 2016; Miyoshi et al., 2025)</p>

<p>Dimerization, AHR/ARNT (KE944) – AHR binding to ARNT.</p>	<p>AhR target genes (transcript): induction of CYP1A1, CYP1B1, or COX-2 mRNA after AhR activation.</p> <p>DRE-reporter (functional): AhR-responsive luciferase reporter activity.</p> <p>ARNT levels (proteomic): Western blot for ARNT nuclear localisation; co-immunoprecipitation of AhR/ARNT complex.</p>	<p>(Gawdzik et al., 2018; Krishna et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2025; Shankar & Villeneuve, 2023; Van Hasselt et al., 2020)</p>
<p>Disruption, Intracellular Calcium Mobilization (KE1536) – Impaired Ca²⁺ release/uptake.</p>	<p>Ca transient abnormalities (imaging): patchy or asynchronous Ca²⁺ signals via Fluo-4 imaging; reduced amplitude or slower kinetics in response to pacing or agonists.</p> <p>SR Ca content (functional): caffeine-induced Ca²⁺ transient; reduced SR release.</p> <p>RyR2/PLN expression (transcript/protein): changes in expression of ryanodine receptor or phospholamban by qPCR/WB.</p>	<p>(Bhutani et al., 2025; Burnett et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2018; Shen et al., 2000; Wells et al., 2019; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Disruption, Sarcomere Assembly (KE1537) – Impaired myofibril formation.</p>	<p>Sarcomere structure (imaging): immunostaining for α-actinin or myosin heavy chain; fragmented or disorganised Z-lines in microscopy. Quantify sarcomere periodicity by FFT analysis.</p> <p>Sarcomeric protein levels (proteomic): reduced α-actinin or cTnT protein content.</p> <p>Contractility (functional): cells with disorganised sarcomeres show lower contraction force and irregular beating.</p>	<p>(Adamcova et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Johansson et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2025; Sharma et al., 2018; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Hypoxia (KE590) – Low oxygen in tissue.</p>	<p>HIF-1α stabilisation (proteomic): accumulation of HIF-1α protein (WB) under low O₂.</p> <p>HIF-target genes (transcript): upregulation of VEGFA, SLC2A1 (Glut1), PDK1 by qPCR.</p> <p>Metabolomic: elevated lactate (colorimetric assay) or reduced ATP (luminescence) due to anaerobic metabolism.</p> <p>Oxygen probes (functional): O₂-sensitive fluorescent dyes to directly measure O₂ tension in organoids.</p>	<p>(Johansson et al., 2020; Krishna et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2025; Mamoshina et al., 2021; Shankar & Villeneuve, 2023; Westerhoff et al., 2025; Wills, 2017)</p>
<p>Increase, Cardiac Remodeling (KE2084) – Structural tissue remodelling (hypertrophy, fibrosis).</p>	<p>Extracellular matrix markers (proteomic): collagen I/III, fibronectin levels by ELISA or immunostaining.</p> <p>Fibroblast activation (imaging): α-SMA staining for myofibroblasts.</p> <p>Matrix metalloproteases (transcript): upregulation of MMP2/9 by qPCR.</p> <p>Tissue stiffness (physical): increased contractile stress on stiffer substrates (as a surrogate for fibrosis).</p>	<p>(Johansson et al., 2020; Lyon et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2025; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Increase, COX-2 Expression (KE1269) – Induction of cyclooxygenase-2.</p>	<p>PTGS2 mRNA/protein (transcript/protein): upregulation of COX-2 expression (qPCR/WB) in cardiomyocytes or endothelial cells.</p> <p>Prostaglandin E2 (metabolomic): increased PGE₂ in medium (ELISA) as COX-2 product.</p>	<p>(Krishna et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2025; Mamoshina et al., 2021)</p>

<p>Increase, slincR Expression (KE2021) – Induction of lncRNA slincR.</p>	<p>slincR transcript (transcript): quantify lncRNA slincR levels by qRT-PCR. (slincR is a noncoding RNA; mechanism in the heart is not well-characterized.)</p>	<p>(Gawdzik et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2022; Shankar & Villeneuve, 2023)</p>
<p>Increased Cellular Proliferation/Differentiation (KE1500)</p>	<p>Ki-67 or EdU (imaging): percent of cardiomyocytes labelled (immunofluorescence or click chemistry) as a proliferation marker.</p> <p>Cyclins (transcript/protein): upregulation of cyclin D/E by qPCR/WB.</p> <p>Population doubling time: growth curve of cell number.</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2018; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Increased Cholinergic Signaling (KE39) – Downstream of KE10 (ACh receptor activation).</p>	<p>Beat rate (electrophysiology): further slowed beating on MEA after muscarinic agonists (carbachol).</p> <p>Bradyarrhythmias (MEA): emergence of AV-block-like pauses.</p> <p>cGMP or NO (biochem): ACh-induced NO release measured by Griess assay or cGMP ELISA in co-culture with endothelium.</p>	<p>(Amend et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Honda et al., 2021)</p>
<p>Increased Atrioventricular Block and Bradycardia (KE444) – Electrical slowing.</p>	<p>Conduction velocity (electrophysiology): MEA measurement of conduction time between electrodes; delays indicate AV block.</p> <p>Beat rate (electrophysiology): average rate reduction on MEA or impedance assays.</p> <p>PR interval surrogate: in ventricular monolayer, pattern of delayed electrical wave propagation.</p>	<p>(Amend et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Honda et al., 2021; Wells et al., 2019)</p>
<p>Increased Cardiac Arrhythmia (KE699/1106)</p>	<p>Beat irregularity (electrophysiology): MEA-detected arrhythmic beats (pause, early beats) or erratic field potential patterns.</p> <p>EADs/DADs (electrophysiology): after-depolarisations seen in patch-clamp recordings.</p> <p>Synchronisation index (imaging): reduced synchrony of beating in multicellular culture.</p>	<p>(Amend et al., 2019; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021)</p>
<p>Increased Cardiac Fibrosis (KE1924)</p>	<p>Collagen deposition (imaging): Sirius Red or immunostaining for collagen in cardiac spheroids/organoids.</p> <p>Fibroblast markers (transcript): upregulation of Col1A1 and α-SMA (ACTA2) by qPCR.</p> <p>Extracellular stiffness (physical): increased rigidity of engineered tissue.</p>	<p>(Lyon et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2025; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Increased Myocardial Apoptosis (KE1918)</p>	<p>Caspase activity (biochem): caspase-3/7 cleavage assay (luminescent) in cardiomyocyte cultures.</p> <p>TUNEL or Annexin V (imaging): % of apoptotic nuclei by TUNEL staining or Annexin V flow cytometry.</p> <p>Pro-apoptotic gene expression: upregulation of BAX and BAD mRNA by qPCR.</p>	<p>(Adamcova et al., 2019; Bhutani et al., 2025; Verheijen et al., 2022; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>

<p>Inhibition of Rapid Delayed Rectifier K⁺ Current (IKr) (KE2100)</p>	<p>IKr current (electrophysiology): patch-clamp measurement of hERG tail current in iPSC-CMs; significant block is a direct marker.</p> <p>APD prolongation (electrophysiology): reduced IKr causes lengthened APD/FPD.</p> <p>hERG expression (transcript): KCNE2/KCNH2 mRNA levels (qPCR).</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Krishna et al., 2021; Li et al., 2016)</p>
<p>Mitochondrial Dysfunction (KE177/40)</p>	<p>Mitochondrial membrane potential (imaging): JC-1 or TMRM dye; loss of potential indicates dysfunction.</p> <p>ATP levels (metabolomic): decreased ATP (luminescence assay).</p> <p>Oxygen consumption rate (OCR): Seahorse assay for basal/ATP-linked respiration.</p> <p>ROS production (imaging): MitoSOX or DCF fluorescence elevated.</p>	<p>(Adamcova et al., 2019; Bhutani et al., 2025; Verheijen et al., 2022; Westerhoff et al., 2025; Wills, 2017)</p>
<p>Oxidative Stress (KE1392/1115)</p>	<p>ROS levels (imaging): DCFH-DA or CellROX fluorescence increases.</p> <p>Glutathione (metabolomic): GSH/GSSG ratio by biochemical assay.</p> <p>Lipid peroxidation (biochem): TBARS or 4-HNE assays.</p>	<p>(Bhutani et al., 2025; Grimm et al., 2015; Westerhoff et al., 2025; Wills, 2017; Zhang et al., 2016)</p>
<p>Prolongation of Action Potential (KE1961)</p>	<p>APD (electrophysiology): longer action potential duration (patch clamp or optical AP).</p> <p>FPDc (electrophysiology): MEA field potential duration, rate-corrected; >10% increase indicates prolongation.</p> <p>EADs (electrophysiology): frequent early afterdepolarisations in AP recordings.</p>	<p>(Amend et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2018)</p>
<p>Prolongation of QT Interval (KE1962)</p>	<p>FPDc prolongation (electrophysiology): MEA FPDc increase (Bazett/Fridericia-corrected) is an in vitro surrogate for QTc.</p> <p>Calcium transient duration (imaging): prolonged Ca²⁺ transient time-to-90% decay correlates with QT prolongation.</p> <p>Multi-parametric MEA (electrophysiology): QT surrogates computed on MEA spikes.</p>	<p>(Amend et al., 2019; Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Lyon et al., 2022; Sharma et al., 2018)</p>
<p>Reduced Dimerization, ARNT/HIF1-α (KE945)</p>	<p>HIF target genes (transcript): failure to upregulate VEGF, GLUT1 under hypoxia by qPCR.</p> <p>HIF-1α protein (WB): diminished HIF-1α stabilisation compared to control hypoxia.</p> <p>ARNT (HIF-1β) levels (WB): decreased ARNT protein.</p>	<p>(Gawdzik et al., 2018; Mamoshina et al., 2021; Shankar & Villeneuve, 2023; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>

<p>Torsades de Pointes (KE1963) – Polymorphic VT related to prolonged QT.</p>	<p>Triggered activity (electrophysiology): after sustained APD prolongation, induction of spiral wave reentry or bi-directional pacing-induced arrhythmia in monolayers (optical mapping).</p> <p>EADs (electrophysiology): high incidence of EADs on patch indicates Torsades risk.</p> <p>Beat irregularity (MEA): complex arrhythmic field potential patterns (TdP-like) in iPSC networks.</p>	<p>(Amend et al., 2019; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021)</p>
<p>Ventricular Remodeling (KE2002) – Structural changes after injury.</p>	<p>Fibrosis markers: see KE1924.</p> <p>Hypertrophy markers: see KE2001.</p> <p>Extracellular matrix deposition (imaging): see KE1924.</p>	<p>(Johansson et al., 2020; Lyon et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2025; Westerhoff et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Activation, AhR (KE18) – Ligand-induced Aryl hydrocarbon receptor activation.</p>	<p>CYP1A1/1B1 mRNA (transcript): strong induction (qPCR) by dioxin-like ligands.</p> <p>AhR nuclear translocation (imaging): immunofluorescence showing AhR in the nucleus.</p> <p>AhR reporter (functional): luciferase under XRE control responds to ligand.</p>	<p>(Gawdzik et al., 2018; Krishna et al., 2021; Shankar & Villeneuve, 2023)</p>
<p>Activation, Inflammatory Cytokines/Chemokines/Cytoprotective Pathways (KE151)</p>	<p>NF-κB targets (transcript): increased IL6, TNFA, and IL1B mRNA by qPCR in cardiomyocytes.</p> <p>Cytokine release (proteomic): IL-6, TNF-α levels in medium (ELISA).</p> <p>Anti-oxidant genes: e.g. Nrf2 targets (HO-1, SOD2) expression.</p>	<p>(Bhutani et al., 2025; Georgiadis et al., 2022; Krishna et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2025)</p>
<p>Activation, Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptor (KE559)</p>	<p>Nicotine-evoked currents (electrophysiology): patch-clamp shows inward nAChR currents in iPSC-CMs (indicates receptor presence).</p> <p>Downstream Ca²⁺ (imaging): nicotine can raise [Ca²⁺]_i in cells (Fluo-4 imaging).</p> <p>Cell proliferation (functional): α7nAChR activation can affect proliferation markers.</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Krishna et al., 2021)</p>
<p>Blockade, L-Type Calcium Channels (KE1529)</p>	<p>ICa,L (electrophysiology): reduced L-type Ca²⁺ current amplitude by patch (nifedipine or verapamil sensitivity).</p> <p>Ca transient amplitude (imaging): diminished Ca²⁺ transients (Fluo-4) when L-type is blocked.</p> <p>Contraction amplitude (functional): loss of contraction (video motion/impedance) with L-type blockers (e.g., amlodipine nearly abolishes beat amplitude in hiPSC-CMs).</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Li et al., 2016; Shen et al., 2000)</p>
<p>hERG Channel Blockade (KE2099)</p>	<p>IKr tail current (electrophysiology): patch-clamp measurement of hERG; block indicates KE.</p> <p>APD/FPD prolongation (electrophysiology): blockade causes AP/QT prolongation in hiPSC-CMs.</p> <p>Arrhythmia risk (MEA): hERG block triggers early afterdepolarisations (EADs) in networks.</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Krishna et al., 2021; Mamoshina et al., 2021)</p>

Impaired Ion Channels (KE697)	<p>Multichannel currents (electrophysiology): patch clamp for Na⁺ (I_{Na}), Ca²⁺ (I_{Ca,L}), and K⁺ (I_{Kr/I_to}) currents.</p> <p>AP waveform changes (electrophysiology): alterations in APD and upstroke (reflect multiple channel effects).</p> <p>Ion channel expression (transcript): qPCR for SCN5A, CACNA1C, KCNH2, etc.</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Colatsky et al., 2016; Honda et al., 2021; Krishna et al., 2021; Li et al., 2016; Sharma et al., 2018)</p>
Inhibition, Cyclooxygenase-1 Activity (KE1103)	<p>COX-1 activity (enzymatic): arachidonic acid to thromboxane assay (colorimetric) in cell lysates.</p> <p>TXA₂/prostaglandin levels (metabolomic): decreased TXB₂ in medium (ELISA) if COX-1 is inhibited.</p> <p>PTGS1 expression (transcript): qPCR for COX-1 mRNA.</p>	<p>(Krishna et al., 2021; Mamoshina et al., 2021)</p>
Inhibition, ETC Complexes (KE105) – Block of mitochondrial electron transport.	<p>Mitochondrial respiration (functional): Seahorse OCR; reduced OCR indicates ETC inhibition.</p> <p>ATP content (metabolomic): drop in cellular ATP (luminescence).</p> <p>Mitochondrial membrane potential (imaging): severe depolarisation with JC-1/TMRM.</p>	<p>(Verheijen et al., 2022; Westerhoff et al., 2025; Wills, 2017)</p>
Inhibition, Sodium Channel (KE584) – Block of Nav channels.	<p>INa (electrophysiology): patch-clamp; decreased peak Na⁺ current (e.g., by tetrodotoxin).</p> <p>AP upstroke (electrophysiology): reduced dV/dt max or slower AP rise.</p> <p>SCN5A expression (transcript): downregulation by qPCR.</p>	<p>(Burnett et al., 2021; Honda et al., 2021)</p>
Cardiovascular Dysregulation (KE1703)	<p><i>No direct in vitro biomarker.</i></p>	<p>–</p>
Decrease, Cardiac Ejection Fraction (KE1533)	<p><i>No direct in vitro biomarker.</i></p>	<p>–</p>

Next-steps

This dataset will go under peer review and validation by a group of expert collaborators of S2TOX. Additionally, they will be matched with available methods from the laboratories partners on this project at the University of Liège, KU Leuven and other partners, and finally, they will ranked by priority before approval for use in *in vitro* assays

Abbreviations

AAS — anabolic androgen steroids

ACh — Acetylcholine

AChE — Acetylcholinesterase

AHR — Aryl hydrocarbon receptor
ANP — Atrial natriuretic peptide
AOP — Adverse Outcome Pathway
AP — Action potential
APD — Action potential duration
ARNT — Aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear translocator
ATP — Adenosine triphosphate
BNP — Brain natriuretic peptide
CAT — Catalase
CK-MB — Creatine kinase-myocardial band isoenzyme
CMs — Cardiomyocytes
COX-2 — Cyclooxygenase-2
cTnI — Cardiac troponin I
cTnT — Cardiac troponin T
DADs — Delayed afterdepolarisations
dV/dt — maximum rate of voltage change
EADs — Early afterdepolarisations
EF — Ejection Fraction
ETC — Electron Transport Chain
FFT — Fast Fourier Transform
FLIPR — Fluorescent imaging plate reader
FPD — Field potential duration
FPDc — Field potential duration, rate-corrected
FS — Fractional shortening
GSH — Glutathione
GSSG — Glutathione disulfide
hERG — human ether-à-go-go related gene
HIF — Hypoxia inducible factor
hiPSC — human induced pluripotent stem cell
I_{Ca,L} — L-type calcium current
I_{Kr} — Rapid delayed rectifier potassium current
I_{Na} — Peak sodium current
I_{to} — transient outward current
iPSC — induced pluripotent stem cell
KE — Key Event
LC-MS — Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry
LDH — Lactate dehydrogenase
LLMs — Large language models
LVEF — Left ventricular ejection fraction,
LVFS — Left ventricular fractional shortening
MDA — Malondialdehyde
MEA — Microelectrode array
MeDIP-seq — Methylated DNA immunoprecipitation sequencing,
miRNA — microRNA
miRNA-seq — microRNA sequencing
MMP — Mitochondrial membrane potential
mRNA — messenger RNA
Nav — Voltage-gated sodium channels
nAChR — Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptor
NF-κB — Nuclear factor-kappa B
NKX2-5 — NK2 Homeobox 5
NP — Natriuretic peptides,

NPPA — Natriuretic peptide precursor A
NPPB — Natriuretic peptide precursor B
OCR — Oxygen consumption rate,
OXPHOS — Oxidative phosphorylation,
PBPB — Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic
PDK1 — Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase 1
PLN — Phospholamban
PTGS1 — Prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 1 (COX-1 gene)
PTGS2 — Prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 2 (COX-2 gene)
qPCR — quantitative polymerase chain reaction
qRT-PCR — quantitative reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction
QTc — Corrected QT interval,
QTcF — Corrected QT interval using Fridericia correction
RAF — Rapidly accelerated fibrosarcoma,
RNA-seq — RNA sequencing,
ROS — Reactive oxygen species,
RyR2 — Ryanodine receptor 2
S2TOX — Mechanistic Assessment of Cardiotoxicity using Integrated *In Silico* and *In Vitro* Modeling
SBML — Systems Biology Markup Language
SCN5A — Sodium channel, voltage-gated, type V, alpha subunit,
SOX9 — SRY-Box Transcription Factor 9
SOD — Superoxide dismutase
SR — Sarcoplasmic reticulum
TdP — Torsade de pointes,
TMRM — Tetramethylrhodamine, methyl ester
TNF- α — alpha-Tumor necrosis factor,
TUNEL — Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick end labeling
TXA₂ — Thromboxane A₂
TXB₂ — Thromboxane B₂
VEGF — Vascular endothelial growth factor
WB — Western blot
XRE — Xenobiotic Response Element

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